

ISSN: 2348-4802

AI-POWERED MULTICROP DISEASE CLASSIFICATION AND SMART PESTICIDE RECOMMENDATION SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Agricultural innovation plays a crucial role in a nation's economic and technological advancement. As the backbone of all economies, agriculture provides essential food and raw materials. However, plant disease detection remains a critical challenge in ensuring food security. While technology has long supported agriculture, the integration of deep learning in crop disease detection has gained momentum in the 21st century, thanks to advancements in computing power and large-scale datasets.

Traditionally, farmers relied on manual inspection and ancestral knowledge to identify plant diseases. Agricultural specialists would assess crops based on visible symptoms and recommend treatments accordingly. Although effective in some cases, this approach was time-consuming, heavily dependent on expertise, and prone to misdiagnosis.

The increasing global population and rising food demand necessitate a more efficient and accurate approach. Deep learning, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs), has revolutionized agricultural disease detection by enabling real-time, high-precision analysis of crop images. Automating this process allows farmers to respond swiftly, preventing large-scale yield losses while optimizing pesticide use, thus minimizing environmental impact.

By integrating AI-driven crop disease detection with precise pesticide recommendations, this approach ensures sustainable farming, enhances food security, and empowers farmers with cutting-edge technology to protect their crops effectively.

Keywords: Crop Disease Detection, Deep Learning, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Precision Agriculture, AI in Farming.

1.INTRODUCTION

The history of multi-crop disease classification and pesticide recommendation systems can be traced to the intersection of agriculture and emerging technologies. In the late 20th century, early attempts to automate disease detection focused on basic rule-based systems. However, the true revolution came with the integration of machine learning in the early 21st century.

As computer vision and image recognition technologies advanced, researchers began applying these tools to agricultural images, enabling more accurate and efficient identification of crop diseases. This laid the foundation for multi-crop disease classification systems, which could analyze images from various crops and distinguish between healthy and infected plants.

Simultaneously, the development of pesticide recommendation systems gained momentum. Initially, these systems relied on expert knowledge and predefined rules. However, with the rise of machine learning algorithms and access to vast datasets, these systems evolved to incorporate dynamic factors such as weather conditions, soil health, and historical disease patterns.

Deep learning models, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs) in computer vision applications, enhance the precision of crop disease detection. By learning intricate patterns and

features within images, these models can distinguish between healthy and infected plants across various crops.

Prior to the advent of computing technology, agricultural scientists relied on manual observation, experimentation, and domain knowledge to identify crop diseases and recommend treatments. The understanding of plant diseases dates back centuries, with early efforts focused on documenting symptoms, identifying pathogens, and developing rudimentary treatments. Agricultural extension services and research institutions played a crucial role in disseminating knowledge about crop diseases and management practices to farmers. The development of computing technology in the mid-20th century provided new tools for data analysis, modeling, and decision support in agriculture. Early computer-based agricultural systems focused on basic tasks such as data management, weather forecasting, and crop yield estimation.

The 1980s saw the emergence of expert systems in agriculture, including disease diagnosis and management. Expert systems were rule-based computer programs that encoded domain-specific knowledge provided by agricultural experts. These systems helped farmers and agricultural professionals make informed decisions about disease identification, treatment selection, and pest management.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

G. K. Srikanth, et al. [1] proposed a method in the abstract involves an integrated and collaborative platform for automated disease diagnosis, tracking, and forecasting in the context of plant diseases. Here are the key components of the proposed approach In recent years, there has been a significant shift towards leveraging advanced technologies like deep learning for predictive modeling in agriculture. One such approach involves utilizing environmental data pertaining to crop growth to develop predictive models for disease and pest infestations.

Maheng, et al. [2] proposed a method for crop disease detection and pest prediction, based on AI and deep learning, involves the following key aspects: through the application of deep convolutional neural networks (CNNs), researchers have achieved an impressive accuracy rate of 99.35% in identified 14 crop species and 26 diseases from controlled leaf images. This breakthrough not only surpasses the capabilities of traditional methods but also addresses critical challenges such as labour costs, accuracy, and environmental impact. Despite these advancements, challenges persist, including data-intensive tasks, processing time, and storage limitations associated with deep learning approaches.

Venkatasachandranth.p, et al. [3] proposed a method for pest detection and classification using deep learning involves the following key aspects: Looking ahead, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and deep learning holds tremendous promise for revolutionizing crop disease management and prevention, ushering in an era of more efficient, accurate, and sustainable agricultural practices."

Ramya N, et al. [4] proposed a method for plant disease detection using deep learning involves the following key aspects agricultural technology advancements, deep convolutional neural networks (CNNs) play a pivotal role. These sophisticated algorithms excel in swiftly recognizing disease indications and symptoms from plant leaves and stems, thereby facilitating the promotion of healthy crop growth. Additionally, employing pre-trained deep learning .

Tirkey, et al. [5] proposed a method utilizes deep learning, specifically YoloV5, InceptionV3, and CNN models, for real-time identification and detection of insects in Soybean crops. Achieving high accuracies of 98.75%, 97%, and 97% respectively, the YoloV5 algorithm stands out for its exceptional speed at 53fps, making it suitable for efficient real-time insect detection. The study aims to streamline agriculture practices by reducing the workload of producers through a simplified yet effective solution.

Ramanjot ,et al. [6] proposed a method for plant disease detection in India, focusing on data sources, pre-processing, feature extraction, data augmentation, and model selection. A comprehensive analysis

of 182 papers from 2010 to 2022 identifies 75 relevant works, providing a valuable resource for researchers aiming to enhance system performance and accuracy in plant disease identification through data-driven approaches.

Ma L, et al. [7] introduced CTR_YOLOv5n, has been improved YOLOv5n model for detecting common maize diseases (leaf spot, gray spot, and rust) in mobile applications. The model incorporates a Coordinate Attention (CA) mechanism and a Swin Transformer (STR) detection head (TR2), enhancing accuracy by 2.8% compared to the original model while significantly reducing memory size to 5.1MB, meeting lightweight requirements for mobile use.

Shoaib M, et al. [8] explored the application of Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) techniques for early identification of plant diseases, addressing the limitations of manual detection methods. Focusing on advancements between 2015 and 2022, the study emphasizes improved accuracy and efficiency in plant disease detection through experimental validation.

Guerrero A, et al. [9] proposed a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)-based model for identifying and classifying tomato leaf diseases in Mexico. Utilizing a public dataset and additional field photographs, the model incorporates generative adversarial networks to mitigate overfitting.

Ahmed I, et al. [10] presented an automated method for early detection of plant diseases on large crop farms using machine learning and deep learning techniques. Utilized the "Plant Village" dataset with 17 diseases across 12 crop species, the study employs support vector machines (SVMs).

Balaji V, et al. [11] conducted a thorough survey of methodologies for detecting rice plant diseases, analyzed various classifiers and strategies employed in studies from the last decade. It proposed a model for rice disease detection utilizing an enhanced convolutional neural network (CNN) to leverage the success of deep neural networks in image classification challenges.

Kirola M, et al. [12] proposed a comprehensive framework for plant disease detection and classification based on leaf symptoms, used machine learning and deep learning techniques. Image acquisition, pre-processing, segmentation, feature extraction, and classification are incorporated in the disease detection method.

S. C. Gopi, et al. [13] proposed utilizing transfer learning models, specifically examining frozen layers and fine-tuning, for automated detection of rice leaf diseases. DenseNet169 with frozen layers achieves a notable testing accuracy of 99.66%, while as a fine-tuned transfer learning model, outperforms with an impressive testing accuracy of 99.99%.

Kumar R, et al. [14] reviewed recent research on fungal and bacterial plant disease detection, focused on computer vision-based techniques. It categorized approaches into machine learning and deep learning, highlighting the utilization of real-field and laboratory-conditioned plant leaf images.

Chen J, et al. [15] proposed method involves enhancing an artificial neural network for image segmentation, utilizing extracted pixel and feature values. Subsequently, a CNN-based model is employed for image classification, achieving an impressive average accuracy of 93.75%.

Chammara, et al. [16] AI Crop CAM integrates edge image processing, IoT, and LoRaWAN for real-time decision support in Precision Agriculture. It employed four DCNN models for crop classification, canopy quantification, plant/weed counting, and insect identification. Tested with >43,000 field images, AI Crop CAM achieves high accuracy and low power consumption, transmitting predictions to ThingSpeak IoT platform for visualization and analytics.

Niroj, et al. [17] introduced a hybrid model for detecting paddy diseases, combining deep learning (VGG16) with machine learning algorithms. It categorized 13 types of diseases and achieves high accuracy (99.9%) by classifying CNN's high-level features using Naive Bayes. This approach reduced the need for extensive image datasets and offers a practical solution for early disease identification in paddy cultivation.

Nahiduzzaman.md et al. [18] his study developed PDS-CNN, a lightweight depth-wise separable CNN, for mulberry leaf disease identification using computer vision. Annotated leaf images are

augmented to generate 6,000 synthetic samples, and the model achieves high accuracies of 95.05% for three-class and 96.06% for binary classifications.

Mehta, et al. [19] Utilized Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model for precise apple disease detection and classification. Integration of object identification, segmentation, and image classification within the CNN, enhanced by data augmentation techniques, Achieved 97.06% accuracy and improved evaluation metrics, facilitating informed decisions for enhanced crop management and increased yields in the apple industry.

Choudharya, et al. [20] conducted an extensive review of machine learning approaches for crop disease detection to assess recent developments and classifications. Addressed the need for automated, real-time, and non-destructive disease detection methods to mitigate economic losses in agriculture. Utilize machine learning for early disease identification to enable timely preventive.

Dixit athul kumar, et al. [21] Conducted a comprehensive review of research papers spanning five years on rice plant disease detection, focusing on machine learning and deep learning algorithms. Identified key challenges and solutions related to plant disease detection, particularly in the context of rice cultivation, leveraging CNN's accuracy in image classification.

P.Kaur et al. [22] Developed a deep ensemble learning model (DELM) for autonomous identification of tomato plant leaf diseases, refining models using transfer learning and augmentation techniques. Evaluate the model's performance using a publicly available dataset containing ten different biotic disease classes, achieving 98% accuracy with VGG16 and improved results with an ensemble of VGG16, InceptionV3, and Google Net.

HI peyal, et al. [23] developed a lightweight 2D CNN architecture to classified 14 disease classes in tomato and cotton crops, achieving high accuracy (97.36%) and outperforming pre-trained models. Implement the model into an android application, "Plant Disease Classifier," enabling smartphone-assisted diagnosis with rapid classification (4.84 ms per image). Utilize Gradient Weighted Class Activation Mapping (Grad-CAM) to visually explain disease detection, demonstrating impressive precision, recall, F1-score, and Area Under Curve (AUC) metrics.

AS kini, et al. [24] Implemented intelligent transfer learning with CNNs to predicted black pepper leaf diseases, utilized deep learning on a newly developed dataset of real-time leaf images. Fine-tune models such as Inception V3, Google Net, Squeeze Net, and Resnet18 with hyper parameter tuning for high accuracy (99.1% to 99.7%), with Resnet18 outperforming others at 99.67%.

M. Agarwal, et al. [25] proposed a method SAM, combined stacked auto encoder (SAE) with ResNet50 for automated rice plant disease detection. SAE reduces learning parameters and complexity, enhancing detection accuracy by minimizing dimensionality. Compared to basic CNN and VGG16, SAM Res Net achieves superior performance, with an accuracy of 97%.

J Vankara, et al. [26] this paper introduced a framework for automating plant disease detection using a tailored deep learning architecture. Leveraging deep convolutional neural networks, the proposed method demonstrates superior performance compared to standard classifiers, offering potential for real-time application.

M Tholkapiyan, et al. [27] proposed an automated diagnosis system for rice-related diseases, employing a hybrid deep learning technique. Image processing and machine learning methods are integrated to enhance disease detection accuracy. Meta-heuristic optimization is utilized to optimize parameters such as dataset size, preprocessing, procedures, and classification approaches.

Chetan.H,et al [28] proposed method involves utilized ResNet-50 for leaf disease identification and classification in banana and sunflower crops. Image pre-processing includes converting RGB to HSV and employing clustering techniques for segmenting diseased regions.

E Li et. al. [29] Obtained maize leaf images from the Plant Village dataset and field-collected datasets from Northeast Agricultural University in China. Pre-processing: Apply image pre-processing techniques to enhance image quality and remove noise. Model Selection: Choose DenseNet121 as the

primary extraction network and design a Multi-Dilated-CBAM-Dense Net (Dense Net) model by integrated multi-dilated modules and the convolutional block attention mechanism (CBAM).

Anusha M. N,et al. [30] Collected images of plant leaves, focused on pepper and potato plants Pre - processing: Apply necessary pre-processing techniques to enhanced image quality and remove noise Model Selection: Choose suitable DNN models for plant disease detection, considering factors like architecture and performance.

MR Cruz, et al. [31] Gathered a dataset of strawberry crop images, including healthy plants and those affected by diseases.Pre-processing: Prepared the images by standardizing size, colour, and quality to enhanced model performance.Model Selection: Choose a suitable Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture for disease detection, considering factors like accuracy and computational.

Ns Patil,et al. [32] Developed a mobile application incorporating the trained CNN model for on-the-go disease detection in strawberry crops..Testing and Validation: Evaluate the performance of the mobile application on real-world strawberry fields to ensure accurate and reliable disease detection

Lu, Quv Thanh et al. [33] Gathered a comprehensive dataset of plant images encompassing various diseases and healthy samples. Standardized image sizes, enhance quality, and remove noise to prepare the dataset for model training Choose renowned CNN models—EfficientNetB5, Mobile Net, ResNet50, InceptionV3, and VGG16—as candidates for plant disease classification.

Shruthi, U., et al [34] Gathered a comprehensive dataset of tomato disease images, including various diseases categorized into different severity levels, along with healthy and negative class images. Pre processed the images to standardize size, enhance quality, and remove noise. Developed the hybrid CNN model, Tom Sev Net, incorporating self-regulated layers and inception layers for enhanced performance in disease diagnosis with severity level

Sv Gudkov et al. [35] Organized the dataset into training, validation, and testing sets, ensuring a balanced distribution of classes and severity levels. Include negative class images to prevent misclassification. Train the Tom Sev Net model on the prepared dataset using the Ada delta optimizer. Implemented techniques such as data augmentation to improved generalization and prevent overfitting.

Srikanth, G. K et al. [36] Created a comprehensive platform for automated disease diagnosis, tracking, and forecasting, integrating mobile app technology with cloud-based image processing. Developed a user-friendly mobile app that allows farmers to photograph affected plant parts for instant and accurate disease identification.

Ramya R., N, et al. [37] Gathered a comprehensive dataset of plant images, including healthy and diseased leaves and stems, to train the deep CNN algorithms. Developed a deep learning-based model using convolutional neural networks (CNNs) such as Res Net and MobileNetV2 to extract information from plant photos and classify leaves as healthy or diseased.

Gentil, C et al. [38] tropical cropping systems, pesticides are extensively used to fight pests and ensure high crop yields. However, pesticide use also leads to environmental and health impacts. While pesticide emissions and impacts are influenced by farm management practices and environmental conditions.

Venkatasai Chandrakanth P et al. [39] Developed a deep learning model trained on large datasets of images to accurately identify and classify agronomic pests affecting plants like peanuts. Utilize advanced image processing techniques to extract key features and patterns associated with pest presence. Evaluate the model's performance through rigorous testing and validation, considering factors such as accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity. Integrate the model into existing agricultural management systems to enable timely and targeted pest control measures, ultimately reducing crop losses and enhancing overall agricultural productivity.

S. Chaudary et al. [40] Evaluated the trained model's performance using separate validation and testing datasets to assess its accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and robustness across various disease

types and environmental conditions.: Integrate the trained model into a user-friendly interface or mobile application accessible to farmers, enabling real-time disease diagnosis and providing actionable insights for timely disease management strategies.

Rajalakshmi B, et al. [41] Gathered environmental data from crop fields using IoT devices, including temperature, humidity, soil moisture, and weather conditions Clean and pre process the data to remove noise and ensure consistency the environmental data with historical disease incidence records to create labeled datasets for training.

PS Thakur, et al [42] Stated that agricultural productivity is significantly impacted by diseases affecting major crops each year, necessitating effective solutions for disease control. However, manual inspection of fields is time-consuming, labour -intensive, and often requires specialized expertise, leading to substantial crop losses worldwide. To address this challenge, smart agriculture solutions leveraging vision-based machine learning techniques have been increasingly deployed for pest and disease management.

Kumar Raj, et al. [43] Splited the dataset into training, validation, and test sets to train and evaluate the models Train the selected models using the training set, fine-tuning hyper parameters and adjusting architectures as needed to optimize performance Validate the trained models using the validation set to ensure robustness and generalization capability.Evaluated the performance of the trained models using appropriate metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.

Raawghm Apong, et al. [44] Conducted a systematic literature review (SLR) to identify relevant studies employing vision-based AI, ML, and DL methods for plant disease detection.Gather data from major academic databases such as Springer, IEEE Xplore, Scopus, Google Scholar, and ACM library, focusing on studies with significant methodological importance.Applied a comprehensive screening process to select studies based on their relevance and methodological rigor, resulting in a final set of 176 studies for detailed review.

Vani, R., G. H. et al. [45] Proposed artificial intelligence-based image processing technique aims to predict early diseases in maize plants, addressing the pressing need for timely diagnosis in agricultural settings. Early detection of crop diseases is crucial for maintaining productivity and ensuring the financial stability of farmers. By promptly identifying and treating plant illnesses, farmers can minimize losses in crop output and reduce reliance on excessive pesticide use, thereby promoting sustainable agricultural practices.

Manavalan R,et al [46] Gathered peer-reviewed articles related to the early diagnosis of grain plant diseases published between 2001 and 2020 from reputable academic data bases.Focus othat address the identification of diseases in maize, rice, wheat, soybean, and barley, which are crucial for global agricultural productivity.

Mengistu AD et al .[47] Identified of Coffee Plant Diseases using Image Processing and Decision Tree Hybrid Approach Integration of Backpropagation Neural Network and Decision Tree for Disease Classification Utilization of Image Data from Ethiopian Coffee Plantations Training and Testing Split with 70/30 Ratio for Evaluation.

Gangwar A et al. [48] employed a customized U-Net model for image segmentation The U-Net architecture is tailored to effectively segment tomato leaves from images Utilizing the VIA tool, masks of leaves are created to facilitate the segmentation process. a convolutional network is utilized for classification. The segmented images are classified into ten distinct disease categories. This network aids in accurately identifying various diseases affecting tomato crops.

Shovon MSH, et al. [49] Ensembled Model Integration Plant integrates InceptionResNetV2, EfficientNetV2L, and exception to enhance robustness and address under fitting issues effectively.Enhanced Architecture: Featuring Global Average Pooling, Dropout, L2 regularization, PReLU activation, and Batch Normalization, Plant achieves superior performance on sparse datasets while mitigating overfitting.

Albattah W, et al. [50] developed region of interest (ROI) acquisition Utilization of DenseNet-77 for enhanced deep key point extract Improved Net ImplementationDenseNet-77 for robust key points extraction. One-stage detector Center Net employed for accurate disease detection and categorization. Utilized of PlantVillage database for comprehensive analysis. Demonstrated superiority in both qualitative and quantitative assessments over contemporary methods.

Ghaashani MSAM, et al. [51] Stated that Tomato Crop Significance Tomatoes hold immense economic importance globally They are vital for the economies of many countries ,However, they are prone to diseases that can devastate production. Deep Learning vs. Traditional Machine Learning Deep learning models have been developed to automate tomato leaf disease classification, While deep learning excels with abundant data, traditional machine learning may perform better with limited training data.

Ahmadh W, et al.[52] stated that plant diseases significantly impact agricultural productivity, leading to yield and quality constraints for farmers worldwide .Economic repercussions include reduced farmer income and increased consumer prices, with severe consequences like food shortages and hunger, particularly in less-developed countries where disease prevention methods are limited The research investigates Directional Local Quinary Patterns (DLQP) as a feature descriptor for plant leaf disease detection, specifically focusing on horticulture .DLQP captures directional edge information by computing grey-level differences based on quinary values in four directions (0°, 45°, 90°, and 135°) within selected leaf image windows. Support Vector Machine (SVM) is employed as a classifier to evaluate the effectiveness of DL

Zakhi SZM, et al. [53] stated the tomato is a red-coloured edible fruit native to the American continent, specifically originating from the region that is now modern-day Mexico. It holds significant economic importance globally as a key vegetable crop contributing to the agricultural sector. Its widespread cultivation and consumption make it a staple ingredient in various cuisines worldwide. Challenges in Tomato Cultivation: Tomatoes are susceptible to a range of plant diseases, including leaf mould, late blight, and mosaic virus. These diseases pose significant challenges to tomato farmers, leading to reduced crop yields and economic losses

Kanuparthi P et al.[54] stated that agriculture serves as the primary sector of the Indian economy, contributing around 18 percent of the overall GDP (Gross Domestic Product). With more than fifty percent of the Indian population hailing from agricultural backgrounds, the sector plays a crucial role in providing livelihoods and sustaining rural communities.

Zhao S et al. [55] stated that crop disease diagnosis plays a crucial role in ensuring optimal crop yield and agricultural production. Timely and accurate identification of diseases affecting crops such as tomatoes is essential for effective management and mitigation of crop losses.Deep learning methods, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs).

Batool A et al. [56] stated that agricultural productivity forms a cornerstone of economic stability, as the economy heavily relies on the output from the agricultural sector. Any decline in productivity due to plant diseases and pests can have severe repercussions on the overall economic health of a nation Challenges in Disease Detection and Management: Plant diseases and pests pose significant challenges to the agricultural sector.

Thangaraj R et al. [57] stated that early and accurate detection of plant diseases is essential to maximize crop yield. Timely identification allows for prompt intervention, preventing the spread of diseases and minimizing crop losses, thus contributing to higher agricultural productivity. Artificial intelligence-based deep learning methods, leveraging vast volumes of plant leaf images, are pivotal in disease detection. However, detecting diseases with limited datasets presents a challenge for deep learning techniques, requiring innovative solutions to ensure effective disease identification.

Krithika P et al. [58] stated that smart organic farming has gained significance in India, emphasizing sustainable agricultural practices and reduced reliance on synthetic inputs. However, challenges such

as environmental factors, temperature fluctuations, humidity variations, and nutrient deficiencies persist, affecting crop health and productivity: Monitoring systems play a crucial role in ensuring the health and vitality of crops in smart organic farming. By leveraging computer-aided image processing techniques, it becomes possible to detect and address issues such as diseases present in plant leaves promptly. This proactive approach enables farmers to take smart organic farming. Diseases such as Alternaria leaf blight, Bacterial wilt, Cucumber green mottle mosaic, Leaf Miner, Leaf spot, and Cucumber Mosaic Virus (CMV).

Padol PB et al. [59] stated that grapes are among the most extensively cultivated fruit crops in India, contributing significantly to agricultural production and the economy. However, the productivity of grape plants can be severely impacted by diseases affecting their fruits, stems, Leaf diseases, often caused by bacteria, fungi, viruses, etc., are a significant concern for grape growers as they can limit fruit production and prove challenging to control effectively.

Trivedi NK et al. [60] Utilized Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for disease identification and classification. Employment of Google Co lab for experimentation with a dataset of 3000 tomato leaf images. Integration of pre-processing, segmentation, and CNN model tuning for accurate disease diagnosis Achievement of 98.49% accuracy in disease prediction and classification Empowerment of farmers through early-stage disease identification. Enhancement of tomato crop yield by mitigating disease impact through innovative technological intervention.

3. PROPOSED SYSTEM

3.1 Overview

- **Importing Libraries:** Importing necessary libraries such as Tkinter for GUI, Matplotlib for plotting graphs, NumPy for numerical operations, OpenCV for image processing, Keras for building and training neural networks, and others.
- **Global Variables:** Several global variables are declared to be used across functions, such as filename, X (input data), Y (labels), model, and accuracy.
- **GUI Initialization:** The main Tkinter window is created with a specific title and geometry.
- **Functions:**
- **UploadDataset:** Allows the user to upload the dataset containing images of crops with associated labels.
- **ImageProcessing:** Processes the uploaded images, normalizes them, and prepares them for training.
- **cnnModel:** Builds and trains a convolutional neural network (CNN) model for crop disease classification. It either loads a pre-trained model or creates a new one using transfer learning.
- **predict:** Allows the user to upload a test image, performs prediction using the trained model, and displays the predicted disease along with the suggested pesticide.
- **graph:** Plots the accuracy and loss graph based on the training history.
- **close:** Closes the GUI window.
- **GUI Components:**
- **Labels:** Display the title and headings.
- **Buttons:** Perform specific actions such as uploading dataset, image processing, model building, prediction, plotting graph, and exiting the application.
- **Text Box:** Displays messages and information about the processing steps and results.
- **Configuration and Styling:** Various configurations such as font, size, color, and placement are set for GUI components to enhance readability and aesthetics.
- **Main Loop:** The mainloop() function of Tkinter is called to run the GUI application indefinitely until the user closes the window.

Fig 3.1 Flow Diagram of Proposed CNN Model

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The dataset management process begins with the `uploadDataset()` function, which allows users to select a directory containing categorized images representing different crop diseases. Once a dataset is selected, the directory path is stored in the global variable `filename`, and a confirmation message is displayed in the text widget.

For image processing, the `imageProcessing()` function loads image data and corresponding labels from stored files (`myimg_data.txt.npy` and `myimg_label.txt.npy`). The images are normalized by scaling pixel values between 0 and 1, ensuring consistency in training. To prevent bias, data shuffling is applied, randomizing the order of images and labels. A sample processed image is displayed using OpenCV for verification.

In the model-building phase, the `cnnModel()` function constructs the classification model. It first checks for a pre-trained model (`model.json` and `model_weights.h5`). If found, the model and its weights are loaded along with training history. If not, a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is built using the Keras Sequential API. The architecture consists of convolutional layers, max-pooling layers, flattening, and dense layers. The model is compiled with the Adam optimizer and categorical cross-entropy loss to handle multi-class classification. Training is performed using the `fit()` method, and the training history is stored for future reference. Once training is completed, the model summary is printed, and the final accuracy is displayed.

For prediction, the `predict()` function enables users to upload a test image for disease identification. OpenCV is used to load and resize the test image, which is preprocessed and normalized similarly to the training images. The trained model then predicts class probabilities, identifying the disease with the highest probability. A corresponding pesticide recommendation is retrieved from a predefined list and overlaid on the test image using OpenCV before displaying the results to the user.

The graph plotting functionality, handled by the `graph()` function, visualizes the model's performance during training. It retrieves stored accuracy and loss values from the training history and plots them using Matplotlib, showing trends over multiple training epochs.

The GUI layout and interaction are managed using the Tkinter library, ensuring a user-friendly experience. Buttons are assigned to various functions, including dataset upload, model training,

image processing, and prediction. The text widget displays messages, updates, and results. Labels, placements, and styling are optimized for clarity and ease of use.

Finally, the exit mechanism is implemented through an "Exit" button, which triggers the close() function, safely closing the main window and terminating the application

Tomato Leaf Mold Tomato Leaf Mold manifests as yellow or brown patches on the upper leaf surface, often with fuzzy white or gray growth underneath, impairing photosynthesis and reducing yield. Fungal spores (*Fulvia fulva*) thrive in warm, humid conditions, requiring proper ventilation and fungicidal treatment for control.

Tomato Septoria leaf spot Tomato plants affected by Septoria Leaf Spot display small, dark spots with light centers on lower leaves, leading to defoliation and decreased fruit yield. Control involves fungicide application and sanitation practices to reduce the spread of spores.

Tomato Spider mites Two spotted spider mite Two-spotted spider mites infest tomato plants, causing stippling on leaves and fine webbing, leading to reduced photosynthesis and yield. Control includes regular monitoring, predatory mites, and insecticidal soaps to manage infestations.

Sl.no	CropDisease	Count
1	Pepper bell bacterial spot	997
2	Pepper bell healthy	1478
3	Potato early blight	1000
4	Potato healthy	152
5	Potato late blight	1000
6	Tomato target spot	1404
7	Tomato mosaic virus	373
8	Tomato yellow leaf curl virus	3208
9	Tomato bacterial spot	2127
10	Tomato early blight	1000
11	Tomato healthy	1591
12	Tomato late blight	1909
13	Tomato leaf mold	952
14	Tomato septoria leaf spot	1771
15	Tomato two spotted spider mite	1676

Fig 4.1 sample UI Application

Header: The webpage has a blue header with the text "AI driven Approach for multicrop disease classification with pesticide recommendation system" written twice.

Buttons: Below the header, there are six buttons with the following text:

- Upload Crop Disease Dataset
- Image Processing & Normalization
- Build Transfer Learning Model
- Upload Test Image & Predict Disease
- Accuracy & Loss Graph
- Exit

Fig 4.2 Selecting Dataset from File Manager

The process of implementing an AI-powered approach for crop disease detection and management begins with selecting the dataset from the local system file manager, as depicted in Fig 10.3.2. This

crucial step involves the user interacting with the file manager interface to locate and choose the dataset containing images of crop diseases for training the model. Once the dataset is selected, as shown in Fig 10.3.3, the system acknowledges its successful loading, indicating readiness for training.

Fig 4.3 Dataset loaded Acknowledgement

Here the dataset is loaded successfully into model in order to train the model

Fig 4.4 Processed Images

After the dataset is loaded, the images undergo preprocessing, as illustrated in Fig 10.3.4 and Fig 10.3.5. Preprocessing techniques such as normalization, resizing, and augmentation are applied to prepare the images effectively for training the model. Following this preprocessing stage, the model is built, incorporating transfer learning, as depicted in Fig 10.3.6. The high prediction accuracy of 98.27% underscores the effectiveness of the transfer learning approach in training the model on the dataset.

Fig 4.5 Image processing completion
Here the image represents the acknowledgement of completion of image preprocessing

Fig 4.6 Building transfer learning model

In the subsequent steps, as shown in Fig 10.3.7, Fig 10.3.8, and Fig 10.3.9, the model is tested by uploading a test image from the local system files. The model classifies the crop disease based on the uploaded image and suggests an appropriate pesticide for management. This real-world application demonstrates the practical utility of the model in diagnosing crop diseases and recommending tailored solutions. Additionally, Fig 10.3.10 provides a graphical representation of the training process, showcasing the iteration-wise accuracy and loss metrics. This visualization aids in monitoring and understanding the training progress and performance of the model over successive iterations.

Fig 4.7 Selecting and Uploading Test Image from File Manager.

On clicking the upload dataset and predict disease button the model asks to upoad a test image from local system files, After uploading test image it gives output as below image

Fig 4.8 Crop disease classification and suggested pesticide

Fig 4.9 Crop disease classification and suggested pesticide

Here the image shows the output of model which classifies the crop disease and recommends the pesticide for that disease

Fig 4.10 Iteration wise Accuracy and Loss Graph

Here the image represents the iteration wise accuracy and loss graph in which x-axis represents iterations and y-axis represents accuracy/loss

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

Conclusion

The project on AI-driven approach for multicrop disease classification with pesticide recommendation system has reached a significant milestone by successfully demonstrating its ability to accurately identify and classify diseases affecting multiple crops. Through the utilization of sophisticated machine learning and deep learning techniques, the system has proven its effectiveness in analyzing

various symptoms and patterns associated with different diseases, thereby providing farmers with timely and precise recommendations for pesticide application.

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